

PROCESSING AND CHARACTERIZATION OF GREEN COMPOSITES WITH CHOPPED KENAF FIBERS AND RECYCLED EXPANDED POLYPROPYLENE

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ABSTRACT

In the present study, the feasibility of using industrial waste plastics expanded polypropylene (EPP) in a natural fiber composite produced by an injection molding process in the absence of extrusion step was explored. The result informs that incorporation of kenaf fibers into both neat PP and recycled EPP significantly enhances the mechanical and thermal properties of the composites. The tensile modulus, the flexural modulus and strength, and heat deflection temperature of kenaf/recycled EPP and kenaf/PP composites were increased with increasing the chopped kenaf fiber content. The results indicate that kenaf/recycled EPP composites exhibit higher tensile, flexural, and impact properties and heat deflection temperature than kenaf/PP composites due mainly to better fiber-matrix distribution in the kenaf/recycled EPP composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Expanded polypropylene (EPP) foams exhibit excellent impact resistance, elasticity, insulation properties, and energy absorption. Hence, they are often used in protective applications and passive safety for packaging of electronic components, food, etc. and personal safety such as helmets, knee-pads, etc. They are also often used as core material for sandwich composite structures used in aircraft, naval, or automotive industries due to their lightness and their great capacity to absorb energy. Kenaf, which is most frequently in natural fiber composite (or biocomposite) materials, exhibits a number of advantages such as acceptable mechanical properties, light weight, low cost, environmental friendliness, etc. over conventional glass fiber reinforcement [1]. Therefore, plant-based natural fibers are widely used in producing biocomposites with a number of thermoplastic and thermosetting polymers [2,3]. Polypropylene (PP) is one of the most frequently used general-purpose thermoplastics in many applications. It can often be processed via extrusion and injection molding processes, in particular with glass fibers and also with natural fibers. A large amount of the EPP has been landfilled and discarded after end-use [4,5]. Many advanced countries have been endeavored to solve environmental problems due to industrial waste plastics [6]. Chemical and thermal processes to reuse such waste plastics including EPP are well-known but they are costly and difficult to use. One of the possible and simple ways to solve such the problems is to develop composite materials with biomass-based reinforcements and industrial waste plastics. Consequently, the objectives of this study are to diagnose the feasibility of using recycled EPP in a biocomposite system produced by an injection molding process, without extrusion process that may cause possibly fiber damages and breakages due to shearing force during extrusion, and also to investigate the effect of chopped kenaf fibers on the thermal and mechanical properties of recycled EPP, comparing to those of kenaf/PP composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

In the present work, kenaf fibers, which were planted, extracted and supplied from Bangladesh, were used as reinforcement. 'As-received' kenaf fibers were of bundle form of 60-70 cm long. The bundles were chopped to 4-7 mm long by using a pulverizing machine (Man Pyung Co., DHS-28, Korea). Commercial polypropylene (PP) beads (SEETEC R3410), supplied from LG Chemical Co., Korea, were used to produce EPP foam. The 'as-supplied' PP beads have the melting point of 170°C, the density of 0.9 g/cm³, the melt flow index of 7 g/10 min, and the heat deflection temperature is 92°C. Waste EPP blocks with some defects and damages, which were made with the EPP foam, were kindly supplied from KOSPA Co., Korea. The waste EPP blocks of a rectangular shape were of 500 mm × 300 mm × 60 mm in size. The EPP blocks were cut to smaller rectangular shapes by using a band saw (ELEKTRA BECKUM, BAS 250 G, Germany) and then finally cut to 4-7 mm in size by using the pulverizing machine above-mentioned. The pulverized EPP waste, which is referred to as recycled EPP hereinafter, was used as matrix resin for making kenaf/recycled EPP composites.

2.2 Composite Processing

Kenaf/recycled composites were produced by using injection molding technique only, without an extrusion step. Chopped kenaf fibers and recycled EPP were sufficiently dried at 60°C for 6 hours in a convection oven. Manually mixed chopped kenaf fibers and recycled EPP were regularly put into the hopper during the injection process. The fiber contents were 10, 20, and 30 wt%. Plastic coupons made of neat PP and recycled EPP in the absence of kenaf fiber were also prepared for comparison, respectively. Injection process was performed by using an injection molding machine (PRO-WD 80, Dong Shin Co., Korea). A number of specimens for tensile, flexural, impact and heat deflection temperature tests for kenaf/PP and kenaf/recycled EPP composites were directly obtained from the injection process.

2.3 Characterization

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JSM-6380, JEOL, Japan) was used to observe fractured surfaces of the composites. All the specimens were coated with platinum. The electron voltage was 10 kV. Tensile tests were performed using a universal testing machine (AG-50kNX, Shimadzu JP, Japan) according to ASTM D638M. The dog-bone shape specimens were used. The load cell of 50 kN was used. The crosshead speed was 50 mm/min. Ten specimens were used to obtain the average value of tensile modulus and strength of individual composites. Three-point flexural tests were carried out using a universal testing machine (AG-50kNX, Shimadzu JP, Japan) according to ASTM D790M. The span-to-depth ratio of each rectangular specimen was 32:1. The load cell of 50 kN was used. The crosshead speed was 5.1 mm/min. Ten specimens were used to obtain the average value of flexural modulus and strength of individual composites.

Izod impact tests of the composites were carried out at ambient temperature according to ASTM D256 by using a pendulum-type impact tester (Tinius Olsen, Model 892, UK). The dimensions of each specimen were 65 mm × 12.5 mm × 3 mm. Each specimen has a 'V'-shaped notch, made by using a notch cutter according to ASTM D256. The test was performed at an impact speed of the pendulum of 3.46 m/s. The impact distance was 610 mm and the impact energy was 12.66 J. The average impact strength was obtained from eight specimens. The heat deflection temperature (HDT) of each specimen was measured with a three-point bending mode by using a heat deflection temperature tester, Model 603, Tinius Olsen, UK) according to ASTM D648. The specimen dimensions were 125 mm × 12.5 mm × 3 mm. The heating rate was 2°C/min. Each HDT value was obtained at the specimen deflection of 0.254 mm under a load of 0.455 MPa.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fractured Surfaces

Figure 1 displays SEM images of the fractured surfaces of kenaf/PP and kenaf/recycled EPP

composites, compared with those of neat PP and recycled EPP. Neat PP and recycled EPP exhibit typical fractured surfaces of thermoplastic resin. On the contrary, the composites exhibit the chopped kenaf fibers randomly distributed in the PP matrix, which is formed from neat PP or recycled EPP by melting during the process, indicating some pull-out fibers, irregularly distributed fibers and poor fiber-matrix interfacial contacts. It seems that such pull-out fibers, irregularly distributed fibers and poor fiber-matrix interfacial contacts were more distinguishable with kenaf/PP composites than the kenaf/recycled EPP composites. This can be explained by that chopped kenaf fiber is much lighter than the commercial PP beads, resulting in that the PP beads can be fed into the hopper of the injection molding machine earlier than the chopped kenaf fibers (feed-timing lag). As a result, a poor mixing between the fibers and the PP matrix possibly occurred. On the other hand, in the case of kenaf/recycled EPP composites, both kenaf fibers and recycled EPP are in a pulverized form. According, they can be regularly fed into the hopper together without feed-timing lag and then mixed fairly. It is believed that the fiber-resin mixing in the kenaf/recycled EPP composite was better than that of kenaf/PP composite. However, it seems that the fiber-resin mixing was not sufficient enough even in the kenaf/recycled EPP composite because the mixing was done in the short barrel with a single screw during the injection process.

Figure 1: SEM images ($\times 50$) of the fractured surfaces of kenaf/PP composites (A-D: 0, 10, 20, 30 wt%) and kenaf/recycled EPP composites (E-F: 0, 10, 20, 30 wt%) with various kenaf fiber contents.

3.2 Tensile Properties

Figure 2 shows the tensile modulus and strength of kenaf/PP and kenaf/recycled EPP composites. The tensile modulus of neat PP was 1027 MPa and it gradually increases with increasing the kenaf fiber content in the kenaf/PP composite, indicating an increase of about 68% at 30 wt%. On the contrary, the tensile strength of neat PP was 30 MPa and it decreases with increasing the fiber content. The tensile modulus of recycled EPP was 1047 MPa and it gradually increases with increasing the kenaf fiber content in the kenaf/PP composite, indicating an increase of about 114% at 30 wt%. On the contrary, the tensile strength of recycled EPP was 30 MPa, same as with the neat PP and it also decreases with increasing the fiber content. Both the tensile modulus and strength of kenaf/recycled EPP composites are higher than those of kenaf/PP composites. That is, the increase of the modulus is higher in the kenaf/recycled EPP composite than in the kenaf/PP counterpart, whereas the decrease of the strength is lower in the kenaf/recycled EPP composite than in the kenaf/PP counterpart. This is ascribed to pull-out fibers, irregularly distributed fibers and poor fiber-matrix interfacial contacts [7], which can be found in the composites with chopped kenaf fibers and neat PP matrix, as described earlier. In particular, it was found that the kenaf/PP composites exhibit more microstructural defects and voids than the kenaf/recycled EPP composites with improved distribution of the kenaf fibers to the matrix.

Figure 2: Tensile modulus (A) and strength (B) of kenaf/PP and kenaf/recycled EPP composites with various kenaf fiber contents.

3.3 Flexural Properties

Figure 3 shows the flexural modulus and strength of kenaf/PP and kenaf/recycled EPP composites. The flexural modulus of neat PP was 619 MPa and it gradually increases with increasing the kenaf fiber content in the kenaf/PP composite, indicating an increase of about 65% at 30 wt%. The flexural strength of neat PP was 14 MPa and it also gradually increases with increasing the fiber content. The flexural modulus of recycled EPP was 649 MPa, which is slightly higher than that of neat PP. It also gradually increases with increasing the fiber content in the kenaf/PP composite, indicating an increase of about 212% at 30 wt%. The flexural strength of recycled EPP is 15 MPa, slightly higher than the neat PP and it also increases with increasing the fiber content, indicating an increase of about 106% at 30 wt%. Due to better fiber-matrix distribution, both the flexural modulus and strength of kenaf/recycled EPP composites are considerably higher than those of kenaf/PP composites. As expected, the increase of the modulus and the strength is higher in the kenaf/recycled EPP composite than in the kenaf/PP counterpart. The flexural modulus result can be explained similarly with the reason given in the tensile result. However, the tensile strength decreases with increasing the kenaf fiber content, whereas the flexural strength increases with increasing the fiber content. It is obvious that kenaf fiber contains a number of cells in the fiber structure, which adversely behave against external tensile stress. It may be said that such the cells do not influence adversely the flexural stress applied along with the thickness direction of the specimen.

Figure 3: Flexural modulus (A) and strength (B) of kenaf/PP and kenaf/recycled EPP composites with various kenaf fiber contents.

3.4 Impact Strength

Figure 4 shows the Izod impact strength of kenaf/PP and kenaf/recycled EPP composites. The impact strength of both neat PP and recycled EPP is 33 J/m and they gradually increase with increasing the kenaf fiber content in their composites. The impact strength of kenaf/recycled EPP

composites is higher than that of kenaf/PP composites. As known, both neat PP and recycled EPP are ductile with high toughness. Kenaf fiber is quite brittle, compared to the neat PP and recycled EPP. It is obvious that incorporation of brittle reinforcement into the thermoplastic matrix results in reduced toughness. In addition, the poor fiber-matrix mixing and interfacial contacts lead to further decrease of the impact toughness in the kenaf/PP composites.

Figure 4: Impact strengths for kenaf/PP and kenaf/recycled EPP composites with various kenaf fiber contents.

3.5 Heat Deflection Temperature

Figure 5 represents the heat deflection temperature (HDT) of kenaf/PP and kenaf/recycled EPP composites. The HDT values of neat PP and recycled EPP are 64 °C and 66 °C, respectively. They gradually increase with increasing the kenaf fiber content in the composites. In the case of kenaf/PP composite, the HDT was about 101 °C at 30 wt%, indicating a remarkable increase about 37 °C. In the case of kenaf/recycled EPP composite, the HDT was about 113 °C at 30 wt%, indicating an even higher increase about 47 °C. Such the considerable increase of the HDT in the composites is due mainly to a reinforcing effect acting along the through-thickness direction of the specimen during heat deflection test under the three-point bending mode. The fiber-matrix mixing and interfacial contacts in the kenaf/recycled EPP composite better than in the kenaf/PP composite, as described above, are also responsible for the increased HDT.

Figure 5. HDT values for kenaf/PP and kenaf/recycled EPP composites with various kenaf fiber contents.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work explores the effect of kenaf fiber on the mechanical and thermal properties of kenaf fiber/recycled EPP composites and also to compare with those of kenaf fiber/PP composites. It is

concluded that the tensile and flexural properties, the impact strength and the heat deflection temperature of kenaf fiber/recycled EPP composites are higher than those of kenaf fiber/PP composites. However, it was found that the chopped kenaf fibers were not sufficiently distributed in the matrix of the composite due to difficulties of successful compounding during injection molding process. It seems that further improvement of the obtained properties would be possible by manipulating the processing conditions and also by surface treatment of kenaf fiber prior to composite processing.

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